

TYPES OF INFORMATION IN THE SEMIOTIC ORDER

Maftuna Sultanova Rashidovna

Urganch State University Master's student

Department Linguistics: English language M221-student of English group

E-mail: Sultonovamaftuna47@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11158646>

Abstract: This article examines the concept of information and the sequence of types of information in the semiotic order in communication processes, and it consists of three parts. The types of information in the semiotic order are explained in the introduction. Linguistic phenomena and the structure of use of each of them in informative speech and determination of tasks. The last part is the conclusion, which summarizes all the information on the topic and gives the audience final thoughts

Keywords: information, speech delivery, cybernetics, semiotic order, conceptual units, substantive, pragmatic

ВИДЫ ИНФОРМАЦИИ В СЕМИОТИЧЕСКОМ ПОРЯДКЕ

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается понятие информации и последовательность видов информации в семиотическом порядке в коммуникативных процессах, и она состоит из трех частей. Виды информации в семиотическом порядке поясняются во введении. Языковые явления и структура употребления каждого из них в познавательной речи и определении задач. Последняя часть – заключение, в котором обобщается вся информация по теме и высказываются заключительные мысли аудитории.

Ключевые слова: информация, доставка речи, кибернетика, семиотический порядок, концептуальные единицы, содержательный, прагматический.

INTRODUCTION

Speech structures in world linguistics, linguistic phenomena in the delivery of information scientific research aimed at studying its activation the world's leading scientific centers and higher education institutions, including the Oxford University Language Centre; University of Harvard, California State University; Universität Bonn (Germany); University of Oslo (Norway); University of Vienna (Austria); Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (Netherlands); Stroudsburg Association of Computational Linguistics (France); Shanghai Foreign Languages University (China); New Bulgarian University (Bulgaria); Dublin City University (Ireland); University of Toronto (Canada); as well as the National of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek Tashkent State Uzbek University named after Alisher Navoi foreign languages, Samarkand State University of Language and Literature Institute, Bukhara State University (Uzbekistan). is going.

MAIN PART

The concept of "information" correct understanding of the essence, especially communication between people important for process research. The concept of "information" is continuous in a number of scientific fields regardless of the fact that it is being used, in its interpretation no consensus has yet been reached. Dedicated to the topic in research, this concept is viewed from different scientific directions is being studied and the definitions given to it a methodological idea that is a priority in this or that scientific school, being described in accordance with the instructions. Information important in the study of storage and transfer processes it is clear that the information was collected in the field of cybernetics. K. E. Shannon published in 1948

"Communication "Mathematical Theory" is a statistician of information laid the foundation for the analysis, of course. However, cybernetics and mathematics in the theory, the symbolic nature of information, its formality aspects are being paid attention to and reported the meaning of the information is ignored.¹

Semantic information is in the known view of the message which transmits the content of the record in the means of characters or listening comprehension is understanding.² Clearly semantic information rather than destroying syntactic information it is used in reasonable quality. Finally, when it comes to pragmatic information, report it his contribution to the emergence of one or another emotion in the addressee it is meant to motivate to perform a certain action. In this case, the transfer of information with some content to the listener including but not limited to this information the purpose of eliciting a relatively positive or negative attitude intended.³ Among the listed types of information in the semiotic order study of semantic information of communication processes important for theoretical and practical description. In a communication situation. One of the requirements is information, its content in a compact form without any damage to the contents transmission. Condensed information is easy to understand combined with the fact that it is easier and stronger to remember will remain.

In modern linguistics, the concept of "information" is leading became one of the conceptual units. It's even a language we also observe in the definitions given to the phenomenon. A.E. Kibrick as noted, "has the characteristic of internal integrity and wholeness is a multitasking language. One of its main tasks one is related to actions performed on information".⁴ In cognitive linguistics, the concept of "information" is also broad spread across the scale and interpreted in a unique way. For example, in the special dictionary, this concept is defined as "linguistic in the process of communication knowledge that is realized and transmitted through forms definition is given."⁵

The concept of "information" is not without philosophical interpretation. According to the philosophers, in the form of the content of the message the displayed information is "highly structured the material exists as a functional property of the system will be" and the form and content characteristics are the same the only information is transmitted through different means.⁶ Philosophers also emphasize the importance of the form of expression of information they don't forget to shoot. But about the nature of this form opinions differ. Expression of information. If it is done by coding, then the code is conditional the system of signs, together with the view, presents the information there is a need to include the rules of the production in this system.⁷ But it is known that information is a complex phenomenon not only a formal (syntactic), substantive and pragmatic feature without possessing, but variation or variation has the opportunity. Its accuracy, freshness, completeness, Subject factor to have indicators such as importance requires. Only a person can fulfill the role of such a subject.

¹ Roberts C. Information structure: Towards an integrated formal theory of Pragmatics // OSU Working papers in linguistics 49: Papers in Semantics. –Ohio: Ohio State University, 1996. – P.24.

² Ўша асар, 13 б.

³ Ўша асар, 13-14 б.

⁴ Кибрик А.Е. Очерки по общим и прикладным вопросам языкознания (универсальное, типовое и специфическое в языке). - 2-изд. –М.: Эдиториал, 2001. –С. 9.

⁵ Кубрякова Е.С., Демьянков В.З., Панкрац Ю.Г., Лузина Л.Г. Краткий словарь когнитивных терминов. –М.: Изд-во МГУ, 1996. –С. 36

⁶ 2 Дубровский Д.И. Проблема идеального. Субъективная реальность. –М.:Канон, 2002. – С. 128-129.

⁷ Соколов А.В. Информация: Феномен? Функция? Фикция? // Философские науки, 1990. -№9. –С.18

CONCLUSION

According to research, information is actually a process, and this process is a subject does not pass without his participation. Information for a person in the form of knowledge possessing and the actions of this person to collect, store, transfer knowledge able to perform. The information system is formed in the human mind and any action aimed at using information is the same performed on a system basis. Information and communication from it is known that it will be a means of organizing processes.

Reference:

1. Roberts C. Information structure: Towards an integrated formal theory of Pragmatics // OSU Working papers in linguistics 49: Papers in Semantics. –Ohio: Ohio State University, 1996. – P.24.
2. Ўша асар, 13 б.
3. Ўша асар, 13-14 б.
4. Кибрик А.Е. Очерки по общим и прикладным вопросам языкознания (универсальное, типовое и специфическое в языке). - 2-изд. –М.: Эдиториал, 2001. –С. 9.
5. Кубрякова Е.С., Демьянков В.З., Панкрац Ю.Г., Лузина Л.Г. Краткий словарь когнитивных терминов. –М.: Изд-во МГУ, 1996. –С. 36
6. 2 Дубровский Д.И. Проблема идеального. Субъективная реальность. –М.:Канон, 2002. – С. 128-129.
7. Соколов А.В. Информация: Феномен? Функция? Фикция? // Философские науки, 1990. - №9. –С.18